

D6.17 Report on the Fourth One Health EJP School

WP6: Education and Training

Responsible Partner: UoS (P23)

GENERAL INFORMATION

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Introduction

The One Health EJP (OHEJP) Final “Summer” School 2022 “Sustainability in One Health – how can it be achieved?” was held from 5th to 7th December 2022.

The event focused on sustainability, since it is at the core of the One Health approach to optimise the health of people, animals, plants, and ecosystems and needs to be at the centre of the training of young One Health scientists and practitioners. Sustainable solutions must be adopted that recognise the importance of animal welfare, biodiversity and ecosystem integrity for overall health and well-being, now and for future generations.

This Final School was organised by the Local Organising team at University of Surrey in Guildford – UK, led by Roberto La Ragione (Professor of Veterinary Microbiology and Pathology at the School of Veterinary Medicine and Head of the School of Biosciences). The event was organised and hosted in collaboration with the OHEJP Work Package 6 (WP6) team and Communications team based at the University of Surrey, UK.

The event was held online to reach a wider international audience. In total, over 200 scientists from countries across the globe participated. The event was a major success as it provided the first international training initiative entirely devoted to sustainability to a multidisciplinary audience of delegates and involved many OHEJP partners as well as OHEJP Stakeholders. The testimonials from the delegates provide telling evidence of the Final School success.

Theme and Overview

In 2021, the [One Health High Level Expert Panel](#) redefined One Health as the following: “One Health is an integrated, unifying approach that aims to sustainably balance and optimise the health of people, animals and ecosystems. It recognises the health of humans, domestic and wild animals, plants, and the wider environment (including ecosystems) are closely linked and inter-dependent.” Sustainability is at the core of the One Health approach and sustainable solutions must be adopted that recognise the importance of animal welfare, biodiversity and ecosystem integrity for overall health and well-being, now and for future generations.

Accordingly, the programme included the following themes:

- How policies can shape the future of One Health.
- The importance of education and training activities for the future generations of One Health professionals.
- The relevance of effective communication and open research for multisectoral collaborations.
- How to turn research ideas into commercial products.

- One Health topics to which sustainability is being applied, in relation to foodborne zoonotic pathogens and antimicrobial resistance being transmitted between humans and animals, or through the environment, and key emerging health threats.

Aims and Objectives

The aims of this Final School were to understand and learn how:

- to effectively communicate scientific outputs for fruitful multidisciplinary and trans-sector collaboration and to engage with the public,
- to translate science into policy and the impact of policies on societies and on public, veterinary and environmental health,
- to take research ideas to market,
- to apply sustainability to research projects.

Accordingly, the Final School aimed to provide insightful presentations from expert speakers about education and training opportunities, commercialisation, communication, sustainability, policy and research projects applications, as well as lively question and answer discussions.

Virtual Format

In order to allow participants from across the globe to attend (including low- and mid-income countries), the 2022 One Health Final School was held as an online event. The event facilitated a variety of talks and discussions between scientists with different expertise and educational backgrounds. The online event participation was facilitated using the Zoom platform. The virtual format also resulted in a significant reduction in costs associated with travelling and accommodation. The reduction in travel also reduced the environmental impact of the event.

Programme Structure

The wide range of 30 speakers explained how the applications of their work could benefit people employed in public health, animal health and food safety sectors and in general for society. One Health EJP PhD students and researchers funded for Short Term Missions described how these travel awards had enhanced their research and transferable skills for professional development.

Invited speakers from the University of Surrey emphasised the importance of commercialisation of research applications to benefit society and the role of Fellowship funding to assist this process. One session focused on effective communication across different audiences and developing collaborations, essential for generating impact. These speakers shared their insights on how to clearly communicate One Health messages in cross-cultural and multi-lingual environments. Three speakers invited to the policy discussions explained the relevance of science to policy translation. We were delighted to

welcome EFSA Chief Scientist, Carlos Gonçalo das Neves, to this session, as he described the improvements required to One Health governance in this post-pandemic era.

Sustainability had its own session since this key theme needed to be specifically addressed. Our One Health EJP Sustainability Deputy leader, Professor Dolores Gavier-Widén, from the Swedish National Veterinary Institute (SVA) advised on adopting sustainable solutions that recognise the influence of ecosystem integrity and biodiversity in One Health issues. Whilst the One Health EJP sustainability strategy will guide stakeholders on using our research outcomes, associated with antimicrobial resistance and zoonotic diseases, to benefit society, the role of the environment in One Health was outside the scope of our programme. During the emerging threats session, some external speakers described how anthropogenic drivers of environmental change, such as habitat degradation, climate change and wildlife trade, affect the epidemiology of zoonoses. Future pandemic prevention depends on recognising the economic value of ecosystem integrity. These discussions demonstrated that multi-disciplinary collaborations are essential to tackle One Health challenges effectively.

Two sessions on antimicrobial resistance (AMR) and foodborne zoonoses were delivered by One Health EJP project leaders and scientists, who discussed the practical applications of this research. These included the development of new diagnostic on-site tools for the detection of AMR markers for zoonotic bacteria; taking a metapopulation approach to analyse the drivers of AMR in French hospitals; using genome sequencing techniques in AMR risk assessment and improving techniques for sequencing of mobile genetic elements for AMR surveillance. The wide range of foodborne zoonotic threats to human health provided a wide diversity of topics: *Toxoplasma gondii* epidemiology, biosecurity measures to control Hepatitis E virus in food production, standardisation and harmonisation of laboratory protocols for detecting specific bacterial and parasitic pathogens, and their subsequent implementation in One Health Surveillance.

Session Chairs and attendees engaged in a lively question and answer session with speakers after the presentations, which led to further valuable debate on key topics.

Experts and Speakers

A wide range of 30 scientists from 16 institutes across Europe, Australia, New Zealand and Brazil were involved as speakers, providing a comprehensive multidisciplinary expertise from veterinary and human medicine to disease surveillance and prevention, from Open research to scientific communication and One Health policies, from microbiology and virology to molecular biology and metapopulation analysis. Members of the OHEJP consortium shared information about our innovative One Health scientific activities (Sustainability, [Science to Policy Translation](#), [PARADISE](#), [ARDIG](#), [WORLD COM](#), [FULL-FORCE](#), [TOXOSOURCES](#), [MATRIX](#) and [OH-HARMONY-CAP](#) projects) and training opportunities ([Short term missions](#) and [Education and training](#) outcomes) across our three research domains, in relation to sustainability. Invited speakers from the University of Surrey (UK), The Australian National University, Anses, Massey University (New Zealand), Animal &

Plant Health Agency (UK), University of Rio de Janeiro (Brazil) DEFRA (UK) and Wageningen University also presented their work to our delegates. The Chief Scientist of EFSA (one of the main [OHEJP stakeholders](#)) also enriched the programme by providing overviews of the challenges for the One Health governance in this post-pandemic era. Our expert speakers explained how the applications of their work can benefit people employed in public health, animal health and food safety sectors and in general for society.

Detailed biographies and photos of the speakers are available on the OHEJP website (<https://onehealthjep.eu/final-school-2022/>).

Logistical arrangements

The organisation of the event went smoothly thanks to the use of the Zoom platform and the support of [Purple Patch](#). All participants received a link to join the event in a timely manner, with instructions. All speakers joined the sessions without problems. Delegates were able to attend presentations and to actively contribute to the discussions using the chat function in Zoom. However, some delegates, particularly those in distant locations such as Nigeria, had occasional issues due to local connection problems. The presentations were recorded, with the speakers' permission and recordings have been made available to the attendees.

The organisation of the event required weekly planning meetings at the University of Surrey, between September and December 2022. These meetings focused on a) identifying the topics of the sessions, b) designing the programme, c) identifying the speakers and contacting them, d) preparing the online event with Purple Patch.

The event took place over three days from Monday 5th to Wednesday 7th December 2022, each day normally from 10am – 1pm and from 2pm - 4pm GMT. Please see programme (Annex 3) for specific daily arrangements. The lecture sessions allowed ample time for questions and comments by delegates in the chat: the chairpersons took care that no questions or comments in the chat were left unanswered.

Finally, permission for photos and recordings, in line with GDPR, were obtained by the OHEJP team from lecturers, tutors and delegates before the event during registration.

Promotional Campaign

The promotional campaign was managed by the OHEJP Communications Team. Several promotional flyers, such as "Save the Date" (Annex 1) and "Registration open" were created and validated with the organising team.

These flyers were promoted and distributed through the OHEJP channels: the OHEJP website with latest new posts shared on 24th October and 29th November 2022; the OHEJP social media channels of Twitter and LinkedIn with posts frequently disseminated

between 6th October and 20th November 2022 (weekly), between 21st November and 4th December (twice weekly) and during the event 5th to 7th December 2022 (daily updates), and the Newsletters (Consortium Newsletter November 2022 and External Newsletter December 2022). [A dedicated Final School webpage](#) was created with key information about the event. The registration for the workshop opened on 24th October and closed on 30th November 2022. Calls for registration were disseminated on OHEJP social media channels and via emails to One Health EJP and the University of Surrey communities and also to the external organisations of IVSA, RCPATH, EVSB, ECVPH, Med-Vet-Net Association, BMA, WMA, IFMSA, RCGP, BES and veterinary colleagues at the Royal Veterinary College (London), Edinburgh and Glasgow Vet Schools. The event and its registration were also promoted via external organisations’ newsletters, which included EFSA “Focal Point,” the One Health Commission “One Health Happenings” and the Wildlife Disease Association’s newsletter during October and November 2022. The Final School 2022 was listed on the “One Health Day” website (hosted by the One Health Commission and One Health Initiative), as an event under One Health Day 2022, the link can be found [here](#).

Once the details of the Final School programme had been confirmed, a detailed full promotional flyer (Annex 2) and an event programme (Annex 3) were created and validated with the organising team.

The flyer and programme were uploaded on the OHEJP Final School webpage and promoted through the OHEJP social media channels. Short biographies and photos of the confirmed presenters were added to the website page as they were received.

Applications and selection procedure

As the workshop was online, all applications from early career scientists with an appropriate educational background were accepted. Registered attendees came from a wide range of educational backgrounds and disciplines. These included veterinary, medicine, engineering, chemistry, pharmaceuticals, toxicology, epidemiology, ecology, agriculture, economics, nutrition, and environmental, social, and biological sciences.

Educational Background

Highest Level of Education

Delegates

In total, 246 scientists from 56 countries across the globe participated, spanning regions of Europe, Asia, the Middle East, Africa, Australia, and the North, South and Central Americas. Registered attendees came from a wide range of educational backgrounds and disciplines, as shown above.

Delegates were in their early career stages with a range of interdisciplinary backgrounds, skills, and experience, all relevant to integrate sustainability in One Health.

Course Evaluation

After completion of the Final School, all participants were provided with an event evaluation form (Google form sent by email) generated and collected by the University of Surrey. Overall, attendees were satisfied with the event, the range of expert speakers and the discussions. They enjoyed learning about rapid sustainability applied to One Health and found the sessions useful and relevant. Most of the participants stated that they would attend an event organised by the One Health EJP.

Certificates of Attendance

Certificates of attendance templates were created by the University of Surrey and distributed to all delegates who had attended the Final School sessions.

Post-event communications

Blog Post

Work Package 6 colleagues worked closely with the local organising team for the Communications Team to create and publish a blog post promoting the successes of the event, disseminated on 13th December 2022.

The published blog post can be found on the One Health EJP website: <https://onehealthjep.eu/fantastic-ohejp-final-school-2022/>. This blog post was shared through the One Health EJP social media channels Twitter and LinkedIn and the external newsletter published in December 2022.

Latest News Post and Social Media

A latest news post was disseminated on 8th December 2022 via the website, to thank all participants attending the event, which coincided with sharing social media posts on Twitter and LinkedIn. Further social media was disseminated on 15th December and 17th January to share attendee testimonials and video highlights from the welcome talk deliver by Prof La Ragione.

Testimonials

Over 30 testimonials were collected through the evaluation forms, which demonstrated the success of the content, delivery, and interactivity of the event.

The event cultivated a collaborative environment between delegates and lecturers from interdisciplinary backgrounds, skills and experience from animal, human and environmental health domains across the globe, providing a true One health perspective.

Examples of Delegate Testimonials collected

Photos

Approval for medical use in the UK

NHS Collaboration with the NHS Berkshire and Surrey Pathology Services
Testing of Clinical Nasal and oral swabs samples using VH platform (HRA – NHS-REC Approval).

Extracted RNAs: 396
Clinical Negative samples: 750
Total Clinical samples: 354
Clinical Positive samples: 354

Sensitivity: 98%
Specificity: 100%
LOD: 1.4 copies/ul

UK Research and Innovation

Coronavirus Test Device Approval (CTDA) obtained after 8 months of testing

Business Development

The seven c's...

Key points to help with effective communication:

- Be **C**oncise
- Be **C**oherent
- Be **C**orrect
- Be **C**omplete
- Be **C**ourteous
- Be **C**oncrete
- Be **C**lear

DISCONNECT

Political/manag. leadership & engagement
Society
Private sector & finances
Science & innovation

Reactive
Uninterested
Unconvinced
Fragmented

TOXOSOURCES: Toxoplasma gondii sources quantified

- Advancing science, filling knowledge gaps
 - Improved understanding regarding epidemiology and molecular epidemiology across Europe
 - Quantitative estimates of main sources and transmission pathways
- New tools and methods
 - Harmonized approaches enabling comparable data
 - Better preparedness to detect and investigate outbreaks and emerging strains
- Unique consortium, multidisciplinary and cross-sectoral collaborations
 - We would not be able to do this alone at any of the institutes; sustainability – funding ends, but this collaboration will not

BfR **ne HEALTH EJP**

Engaging with stakeholders to translate science into policy, the example of the One Health EJP

Ludovico Sepe
Collaborator of One Health EJP WP5
Science to Policy Translation

Sustainability in One Health

Looking forward to a sustainable future - how do livestock productivity, health, efficiency and consumer perceptions interact?

Economic Viability
Social Acceptability
Environmental Responsibility
Ecosystem health

Permission to publish these photos was obtained during the event registration process. The face and names of any participants or lecturers who had not provided permission were blurred to adhere to the GDPR regulations.

Internal Events Survey information

The European Commission (EC) requires all dissemination and communication activities, and events to be reported. This information has been reported through the [Internal Events Survey](#) on the OHEJP website, which collects data and is reported to the EC.

Name of the activity:	One Health EJP Final school 2022
Date:	5 th to 7 th December 2022
Place:	Online (Zoom)

Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	No
Organisation of a Workshop	Yes	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	
Flyer	Yes	Pitch Event	No
Training	Yes	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	Yes	Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	Yes	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	275	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	1		

Annex 1: "Save the Date" Promotional Flyer

Save the Date!
One Health EJP Final School 2022
Sustainability in One Health:
how can it be achieved?

Date: 5th - 7th December, 2022
Location: Online
Audience: Early career researchers (post-doc, PhD, junior staff members) throughout the EU and from neighbouring areas involved in all aspects of One Health including biological as well as environmental hazards
Fee: free
Registration: [here](#)

[@OneHealthEJP](#) [ONE Health EJP](#)
[#OneHealthEJP](#) [#OHEJPFinalSchool2022](#)

Annex 2: Full Promotional Flyer

One Health EJP Final School 2022
Sustainability in One Health:
how can it be achieved?

Date: 5th - 7th December, 2022
Location: Online
Audience: Early career researchers (post-doc, PhD, junior staff members) throughout the EU and from neighbouring areas involved in all aspects of One Health including biological as well as environmental hazards
Fee: free

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Aims of the Final School
 Over the last five years, the One Health EJP has facilitated transdisciplinary and cross-sector research collaborations to better prevent, predict, detect and respond to global health threats of the 21st Century. Our successful research outputs and education events have demonstrated the importance of communication and coordination between the different partners to advance One Health. This Final School aims to communicate how the outcomes from our innovative and visionary European programme can benefit the future of One Health. The legacy of the OHEJP will continue beyond 2023 through the sustainability plan. Our One Health future will be driven by students and early career researchers, who are invited to this event.

The programme will include:

- One Health topics to which sustainability is being applied. In relation to foodborne zoonotic pathogens and antimicrobial resistance being transmitted between humans and animals, or through the environment, and key emerging health threats.
- How policies can shape the future of One Health.
- The importance of education and training activities for the future generations of One Health professionals.
- The relevance of effective communication and open research for multisectoral collaborations.

Am I Eligible?
 Bachelor's, Masters and PhD Students and early career researchers (e.g. post-doctoral researchers, new lecturers etc.) from both within the One Health EJP consortium and external to the consortium are eligible to apply for the Final School. Applicants should have experience in a relevant field of veterinary, medical or biological sciences (including environment and food sciences).

How can I apply?
 To apply, please complete the application form [here](#).
 The deadline to apply is 30th November 2022.

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[#OneHealthEJP](#) [#OHEJPFinalSchool2022](#)

Annex 3: Event Programme

One Health EJP Final School 2022: Sustainability in One Health: how can it be achieved? PROGRAMME

In 2021, the One Health High Level Expert Panel redefined One Health: "One Health is an integrated, unifying approach that aims to sustainably balance and optimise the health of people, animals and ecosystems. It recognises the health of humans, domestic and wild animals, plants, and the wider environment (including ecosystems) are closely linked and inter dependent."

Sustainability is at the core of One Health approach. Sustainable solutions must be adopted that recognise the importance of animal welfare, biodiversity and ecosystem integrity for overall health and well-being, now and for future generations.

Monday 5th December

10.00-10.15 CET	Welcome and course introduction Roberto La Ragione, One Health EJP Education and Training Leader, University of Surrey, UK
10.15-10.30	Introduction to the One Health European Joint Programme outputs and the future Hen Imberechts, Scientific Coordinator One Health EJP, Sciensano, Belgium
10.30-11.00	Importance of training and education for the future of One Health Dan Horton, School of Veterinary Medicine, University of Surrey, UK
11.00-11.15	Coffee break
11.15-12.00	Short Term Missions: outcomes and insights from researchers who have undertaken OHEJP Short Term Missions Laura Gonzalez Vilella, University of Surrey, UK Ingrid Cardenas Rey, Wageningen Bioveterinary Research, The Netherlands Liam Burke, University of Galway, Ireland Antonio Rodriguez, INIA, Spain
12.00-13.00	An umbrella talk by the University Of Surrey Innovation Department: commercialisation and fellowship opportunities Geoffrey Knoll, Innovation Strategy, University of Surrey, UK
13.00-14.00	Research application into commercial products Johanna von Gerichten, Research Fellow, University of Surrey, UK Aurore Poirier, Research Fellow, University of Surrey, UK
14.00-16.00	The importance of effective communication and collaboration Elaine Campbell, One Health EJP Communications Team, University of Surrey, UK Robyn Alders, Development Policy Centre, Australian National University Christine Daoutis, Open Research, University of Surrey, UK Julie Shapiro, Anses, France

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One Health EJP Final School 2022: Sustainability in One Health: how can it be achieved? Tuesday 6th December

10.00-10.30 CET	What is sustainability? The One Health EJP approach to sustainability and One Health Dolores Gawron-Widen, One Health EJP Sustainability Deputy Leader, SVA, Sweden
10.30-11.00	Interdisciplinary sustainability Lorenzo Fioravanti, Institute for Sustainability, University of Surrey, UK
11.00-11.15	Coffee break
11.15-13.00	Invited speakers: Emerging Threats Arran Folly, APHA, UK Manuel Ruiz Aravena, Cornell University, USA David Hayman, Massey University, New Zealand Mariana M Vale, University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil
13.00-14.00	Lunch break
14.00-16.00	Policy session Helen Roberts, DEFRA, UK Megan Lynch, Open Innovation, Oxford University, UK Francesca Martelli, APHA, DEFRA, UK Carlos Goncalo Das Neves, EFSA Chief Scientist, Director for Research and Internationalisation at Norwegian Veterinary Institute

Wednesday 7th December

10.00-12.00	Invited Speakers: Antimicrobial Resistance Muna Arqum, One Health EJP eLITE Project Leader, APHA, UK Arnoud van Vliet, One Health EJP WORLDCDM project collaborator, University of Surrey, UK Julie Shapiro, Anses, France Pieter-Jan Ceyssens, One Health EJP FULL FORCE Project Leader, Sciensano, Belgium
12.00-13.00	Lunch break
13.00-15.00	Invited speakers: Foodborne Zoonoses Pikka Jovelainen, One Health EJP FOODSOURCES Project Leader, SSI, Denmark Sophie Roussel, One Health EJP LISTADAPT Project Leader, Anses, France Guido Bernadelli, One Health EJP M&I (3) Project Leader, SSI, Denmark Nada Hosten, One Health EJP ONE-HEALTH-TOY-CAN Project Leader, SSI, Denmark
15.00-15.30	One Health EJP Final School closing comments Roberto La Ragione, One Health EJP Education and Training Leader, University of Surrey, UK

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